

PEOPLE ARE CONSUMING CONTAMINATED WATER

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Abstract. This article is about water consumption of people in the world and in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This article contains various information and interviews with relevant officials.

Key words: Water, consumption, system, rivers, wastewater, sanitary rules, treatment.

ЛЮДИ ПОТРЕБЛЯЮТ ЗАГРЯЗНЕННУЮ ВОДУ

Аннотация. В данной статье речь идет о потреблении воды населением мира и Республики Узбекистан. Эта статья содержит различную информацию и интервью с соответствующими чиновниками.

Ключевые слова: Вода, потребление, система, реки, сточные воды, санитарные правила, очистка.

People are consuming contaminated water. 44% of existing centralized wastewater networks in Uzbekistan have become unusable. Nig'matilla Yo'ldashev said that the water coming through the old sewage system is joining the underground water. At the 19th plenary session of the Senate, Nig'matilla Yo'ldoshev criticized the fact that 88% of the water treatment facilities belonging to the state unitary enterprise "Suvoqava" are not functioning. Due to the lack of water treatment facilities in most of the enterprises, the waste water from biological and chemical treatment is discharged directly into rivers and streams.

For example, 44 out of 87 enterprises belonging to the joint-stock company "Uzbekneftgaz" do not have water treatment facilities, says the chairman of the Senate. According to Yo'ldoshev, most of the waste water coming out of 406 enterprises belonging to "Uzcharmsanoat" association and 206 enterprises of "Uztoqimachilik sanoat" is directly discharged without settling and purification. is being thrown into the sewer.

"As a result, sanitary rules and hygiene standards are seriously violated in the areas adjacent to these enterprises. In particular, people are consuming water saturated with harmful substances. Already, when analyzing the wastewater coming out of 58 water treatment facilities in the country, the level of harmful substances compared to the established norms it is determined that it is several tens of times higher. Official structures do not show enough initiative to effectively solve such vital problems," says Yo'ldoshev.

In 2017 - 2018, a solution to this urgent problem was found, and a water filter device that

cleans vodapravod water coming through the sewage system at the molecular level in 5 stages was imported to Uzbekistan from South Korea and continues to be presented to the public.